

EELISA

European University

**EELISA INNOCORE EELISA MULTI LABS (SHARING FACILITIES
& EQUIPMENT)**

**Deliverable 2.3 - Definition of a roadmap on research
infrastructures**

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Türkiye
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

The main objective of this Task is to draw a roadmap allowing the harmonic development of research infrastructures within the EELISA consortium. To define such a roadmap we made use of the information gathered in Innocore WP4 (Multi Labs “sharing facilities & equipment”), devoted to find more technical solutions concerning the visibility and sharing of infrastructures within EELISA.

The general objective of this Task is declined through two interlinked actions :

1. foreseen how, within the EELISA consortium, a consistent strategy for the development of new local facilities can be attained, and
2. defining how facilities that would require a joint effort of several EELISA partners in order to be build and jointly managed, can be identified and implemented.

From the data collected, it clearly emerged that research infrastructures are mostly resulting from the activity of research groups and that any type of roadmap for the coordination of existing facilities or the implementation of novel joint infrastructures should follow a bottom-up strategy. Only in such a way, we will be able to efficiently coordinate the implementation of research infrastructures among the different nodes and to foster the setup of joint facilities relying on the expertise of the researchers of different EELISA nodes, and thus finally to create more sustainable links between researchers and obtain a higher degree of collaborative research between the EELISA partners.

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Review and quality check by EELISA

In order to guarantee coordination and complementarity and avoid overlapping between the two projects, the following people from EELISA have been consulted for the production of this deliverable: SSSA.

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

KER. Key Exploitable Results. We refer to the research outputs with major potential for being exploited within the project.

KPIs. Key Performance Indicators

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

Research Infrastructures. The term “Research infrastructures” includes any piece of equipment that might be available to ‘customer’ whether they are in a laboratory (commercial device or developed/customed by researchers themselves), on a platform.

Research Structures. The term “Research Structures” includes the research centres, research hubs, research groups and research labs, institutes with a research focus, which produce significant research outcomes and thereby, represent a R&I capacity.

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 44 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years, and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a collective strategic research area and research infrastructure map (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 Rationale and purposes

The development of an EELISA strategy for the implementation of research infrastructures has been explored as one of the possible vectors to create links and a convergent research strategy between the partners of our consortium. This is the reason why a roadmap on developing common research infrastructures, beside allowing for a better use of the funds dedicated to infrastructures and equipment thanks to the coordination in their implementation and to the avoiding of duplication of existing resource, it is expected also to yield to an increased opportunity to strengthen or create research collaborations.

The main objective of this Task is to draw a roadmap for the harmonic development of research infrastructure within the EELISA consortium. To define such a roadmap we made use of the information gathered during all project duration in WP4 of InnoCORE. WP4 (Multi Labs “sharing facilities & equipment”) was indeed mainly devoted to find practical solutions to enhance the visibility and sharing of infrastructures within EELISA but also provided an overview on the different practices and funding opportunities existing in each of the partner institutions.

The general objective of the present task has been declined in two actions:

- 2 a consistent strategy for the development of new local facilities can be attained within the EELISA consortium;
3. defining how facilities that would require a joint effort of several EELISA partners in order to be built and jointly managed, can be identified and implemented.

In the following, we will first summarize the information collected in WP4 concerning the existing facilities and funding sources for the new and shared ones, before proposing a roadmap for their future development.

3 An overview of existing EELISA Research Infrastructures: diversity and complexity

To analyse the landscape of research infrastructure existing within the EELISA Alliance, we proceeded as a first step collecting information about existing facilities, infrastructures and technological platforms present within the EELISA consortium. This work (object of the D4.1 task) was performed through a survey distributed by each EELISA partner among its relevant community (i.e. academic staff and/or platform/technical managers). For a detailed description of the outcome of the survey, please refer to the integral information reported as deliverable D4.1.

The survey allowed to get the most relevant technical information about the existing research infrastructures and their accessibility (such as responsibility, characteristics, load, possibility of access) but also essential information allowing to connect each infrastructure to the strategic research areas defined within EELISA WP2.

During this mapping procedure, a diversity of situations was clearly appearing. UPM was the only partner possessing already a detailed mapping of existing facilities² (thanks to a work started at UPM two years before the EELISA mapping and still on-going), while all other partners at the time did not have any centralized information, BME being actually the only

² cf. <https://www.upm.es/recursosidi/>

partner working on its own catalogue. Consequently, the information gathering was biased by a vast majority of facilities from a single partner (UPM 142 over 220 now present on the survey). Nonetheless, some interesting information can be extracted from this mapping: a large majority of facilities is actually accessible for research activity (215 over 220) and many of the Strategic Research Area are represented in the catalogue (as shown in Figure 1 a).

a)

b)

Figure 1 – a) Strategic research areas (SRA) for the collected research facilities and b) Preferred conditions of access for the facilities (not including UPM ones). Both figures are extracted from D4.1

While it is not surprising that some research areas (ex. such as “social science and humanities” or “culture creativity and inclusive society”) are less represented, it is important to stress that among the technologically oriented SRAs, several are almost equally represented, underlying the large spectrum of activity of the consortium. Therefore, a simplistic strategy for future development relying on the identification of SRA underrepresented in terms of research facilities or possessing a very strong potential (number) of infrastructures seems not straightforwardly applicable to our consortium.

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From the perspective of defining a roadmap on infrastructure, it was also important to analyse if already established rules of access did exist. If one except all facilities belonging to the UPM (for which established rules of access already exist), our survey pointed out that practically 2/3 of all other facilities have no pre-defined access rules. More interestingly, when asked about the conditions of access they would prefer, the answers provided by the responsible of each facility (that are all except the UPM ones) show a significant dispersion with responses ranging from “free in the case of a common research project” to “for a predefined cost” , a situation that is already prefiguring the difficulty of defining a common general framework sharing and opening conditions.

Finally, another type of information that is important when aiming in defining a roadmap for novel infrastructure is knowing the availability of those already existing especially in the case of an Alliance such as EELISA which is mostly composed by research-intensive institutions. Indeed, the data collected in D4.1 (Figure 2) show that 42% of the facilities has a very high load, the remaining relatively available to be used, with only 18% loaded at less than 50% of the time available.

Figure 2 – Current load of EELISA facilities from the survey performed in WP4 (D4.1)

Overall, the survey also showed a concrete interest of the researchers in opening their research infrastructures to foster research collaborations although these may take different forms (from collaboration or research exchange to service).

Nonetheless, the diversity of the research infrastructure that were mapped if from one side is definitely a positive aspect since, through sharing of the existent facilities, it will enlarge the possibility and tools offered to the researchers of each EELISA partner also represent a danger for a fluid research exchange and for any type of coordination policy around infrastructure.

The last point is clearly showing up when comparing the administrative rules that regulate the use (ex. type of activity, financial rules, safety, security, quality etc). This work was performed and is fully detailed in Deliverable D4.2. Currently, only 2 EELISA members have set up rules for their infrastructure's facilities at university level: UPM and ITU. Otherwise for the other partners , facility managers or researchers do not have a predefined set of rules when developing collaborations and the rules defining the possibility to share a facility depend on several different parameters such as the type of ‘customer’(academic or industrial), the localisation of the customer (within the structure hosting the facility or within the same University, within the same country etc) or the purpose of the collaboration (teaching, research collaboration, innovation, service). This diversity of rules encountered stems from the fact that our target are research infrastructures which highly research added value. Actually, this kind

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of infrastructures are mainly run directly by researchers or technical staff embedded in research structures while only fewer of them correspond to research platforms directly linked and financed centrally by the University partners, for which it is expected that the application of uniform rules may be easier to impose.

Considering the diversity of situations, the discussions among the partners conducted in WP4 ended up on a common consensus that an effective way enabling to respect the diversity in the structure and to setup a common framework for shared infrastructures would be to agree on the following basic principle (refer to Deliverable D4.2): *any EELISA researcher or academic requesting access to a piece of equipment hosted in another EELISA member and available in the EELISA catalogue shall be considered as an internal user of this piece of equipment.*

In the framework of Deliverable 4.2 we were mainly focusing of the existing facilities shared between the partners but clearly this rule may be extended without additional burden to future facilities. The advantages of this simple approach are twofold: 1) the autonomy of facilities is preserved and 2) all the local and peculiar situations are respected.

Of note to fully implement this rule each institution will have to refer to its own decision-making process to identify possible administrative burdens. Indeed, all partners will have to review and adopt the rules according to their own legal framework.

4 Tools for coordinated infrastructure development

First let us specify that here we explicitly focus on research-driven equipment/platforms while during the mapping procedure (and in the resulting catalogue of infrastructure produced (D4.1)) we let open the possibility of including also routine service platforms or even single equipment. Indeed, the first aim of the catalogue was to increase visibility of infrastructure/equipment-related activities in the EELISA partnership.

Here we want to draw a roadmap for the harmonic development of research infrastructures within the EELISA consortium through a consistent strategy for the development of new local facilities of each partner, and possibly the implementation, of facilities requiring a joint effort of several EELISA partners. Of note this effort may take different forms ranging from a direct financial support but also by a widening of the users community among the EELISA partners that may represent a real added value either from the scientific point of view (the other partners bring the necessary expertise and competences to build and employ the facility) or from an impact point of view (the other partners can be additional users of the funded facilities).

An analysis of the sources of funding specifically devoted to research infrastructures and equipment (performed in Deliverable 4.4) showed how the calls available at regional, national or European level are relatively limited and that different countries face different situations.

The work performed in WP4 pointed out a large parts of the facilities are implemented by relying on a bottom-up approach although this does not exclude that for specific infrastructures such as, for example, those considered strategic for each EELISA partner or service platforms, a top-down procedure implying a central decision made by each partner can be operational.

Of course, this fact renders the coordination of the actions more difficult at the Alliance level since Strategic decisions cannot be made without information and support from the researchers' community.

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For these reasons, the roadmap on infrastructure we provide focuses on the respect of a bottom-up approach and of the central role played by the researchers' community.

First, what are the tools we have setup and that can be used or ameliorated to develop our future infrastructures?

Let's us first focus on how to obtain a harmonic development of local infrastructure at each node though actions that will not reduce the freedom of the researchers nor significantly increase the administrative burden or engage an increase of funding at the University level.

First, we would like to stress that having the same type of facility at several EELISA nodes is not necessarily negative if these facilities are almost full-time used. This is actually the case for service platforms that are routinely needed and for which a close proximity of the research groups is required.

Excluding the setting of this type of research infrastructure, the EELISA researcher willing at setting a novel research facility at each node should be encouraged to use the EELISA research facility catalogue to check if a similar facility already exists in the EELISA network. If this is the case, the corresponding manager should be contacted (thanks to the related contact form) inquiring for its availability and possibly to share best practices in its implementation and managing. The host institution may formally require a proof that this type of check on the EELISA catalogue has been performed, prior to allow acquisition of the facility, to enforce this practice.

The quality (that is completeness and up-to-date nature) of the information gathered in the catalogue of the infrastructure together with its exhaustive nature will thus be of primary importance for a successful implementation of this strategy.

Our futures actions should be focused to increase the visibility of the catalogue among our researchers and to encourage its use and its maintenance.

Concerning the implementation of future joint infrastructures, in Deliverable 4.5 of WP4 we have defined a process (and its implementation) allowing to practically seek for support from other partners for the setup joint infrastructures. This process is based on the use of a simple form enabling to share the information concerning projects of implementation of new facilities and eventually seek for support. The full process is detailed in Deliverable 4.5 of WP4. Here we just want recall that this process is relatively light although we have identified the necessity local referent persons for infrastructure at each node to allow for a fluid dissemination of the information.

5 Towards a coordinated bottom-up infrastructure strategy: a roadmap

The work performed by the members of WP4, briefly summarized in the previous sections, allowed to highlight some main points concerning a possible strategy for coordinated infrastructure development that can be considered as a roadmap for future EELISA research infrastructure.

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Starting from a central and consensual observation that research infrastructure projects are essentially the results of a bottom-up approach where the researchers/research groups play the main role for proposition, the roadmap for infrastructure development we propose has as objective to coordinate the implementation of local and shared infrastructures through the following actions:

- 1) Enhance the visibility and the sharing of knowledge around infrastructures among the researchers' community. Only through a fluid exchange of information between the researchers the new projects can reach an Alliance level and obtain support/involvement of the other member of the Alliance

Tools and possible practical implementation: maintain up to date and enrich the catalogue of EELISA infrastructures, stabilize the associated IT-tools so to grant each EELISA researcher an easy access to the information (including the forms to contact responsible for existing facilities and to seek for support for the implementation of joint facilities, for instance). As KPI a target of 20 facilities per partners included in the catalogue in a one year horizon can be envisaged.

- 2) Encourage the creation of an EELISA community of researchers and managers of facilities to share best practices and to guarantee a long-term future for the different actions. Allow the participation to this community of institutional representatives of each partner (example VP research or similar) enabling to feed and guide the discussion concerning strategic areas for the development of novel shared infrastructures.

Tools and possible practical implementation: animation of the communities through workshops and/or mobility actions related to infrastructures (for instance in the framework of WP9 actions in EELISA2).

- 3) Guarantee a fluid and effective transfer of information at the institutional level to allow researchers to be informed of possible granting sources in real time

Tools and possible practical implementation: Maintain the involvement of infrastructure referent persons and increase their contact and exchange with institutional scientific responsible at each node (such as VP research or similar).

- 4) Pilot and guarantee the application of the sharing rules defined in D4.4 based on the distinction or internal or external users so to apply it to all new and shared facilities

Tools and possible practical implementation : Each partner should refer to its own decision making process to identify possible administrative burdens, review and adopt the rules defined in D4.4 according to their own legal framework. Each partner should also clarify the actual rules of access for the existing infrastructure.

- 5) boost the development of infrastructures for which locally (that is at each node) there is scientific expertise of recognized excellence but not a sufficient critical mass so that a larger public of users belonging to other EELISA nodes is necessary to obtain funding or justify locally the investment of resources

Tools and possible practical implementation : make use of IT Tools to seek for collaboration (see point 1)

- 6) boost the development of infrastructures for which the scientific expertise needed is shared between the nodes by identifying the place and fundings that render their implementation more fluid and efficient

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Tools and possible practical implementation : make use of IT Tools to seek for collaboration (see point 1); Maintain the involvement of infrastructure referent persons and increase their contact and exchange with institutional scientific responsible at each node

In summary, more than identifying a priori specific strategic areas where the partners of the EELISA consortium will agree to jointly invest using a top-down approach, we believe that the roadmap here highlighted will enable each of the EELISA partners to better to develop its research strategy allowing them to benefit from the other partners expertise. In a longer term, we expect that research synergies will emerge naturally leading to unprecedented projects at the Alliance level, whose implementation would not have been possible without the other partners.

Of course, these objectives are ambitious since they will only be possible if an active community of researchers will be created around infrastructure. Beside time, this will definitely require investment to allow a perfect implementation of the tools, their advertising and could, of course, be boosted by specific actions such as mobility calls or workshop opened to users/developers and manager of infrastructures.

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